

Comparison of the Crystallization Behavior of Fe-Si-B-Cu and Fe-Si-B-Cu-Nb-Based Amorphous Soft Magnetic Alloys

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Abstract

The role of the solute elements, copper, and niobium, on the different stages of devitrification or crystallization of two amorphous soft magnetic alloys, $\text{Fe}_{73.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Nb}_3\text{Cu}_1$, also referred to as FINEMET, and a $\text{Fe}_{76.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Cu}_1$ alloy, a model composition without Nb, has been investigated in detail by coupling atom probe tomography and transmission electron microscopy. The effects of copper clustering and niobium pile-up at the propagating interface between the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ nanocrystals and the amorphous matrix, on the nucleation and growth kinetics have been addressed. The results demonstrate that while Cu clustering takes place in both alloys in the early stages, the added presence of Nb in FINEMET severely restricts the diffusivity of solute elements such as Cu, Si, and B. Therefore, the kinetics of solute partitioning and mobility of the nanocrystal/amorphous matrix interface is substantially slower in FINEMET as compared to the $\text{Fe}_{76.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Cu}_1$ alloy. Consequently, the presence of Nb limits the growth rate of the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ nanocrystals in FINEMET and results in the activation of a larger no. of nucleation sites, leading to a substantially more refined microstructure as compared to the $\text{Fe}_{76.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Cu}_1$ alloy.

1. Introduction

Over the past 20 years, there has been great interest in partially de-vitrified amorphous materials, such as the FINEMET alloy with the composition $\text{Fe}_{73.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Nb}_3\text{Cu}_1$. This alloy exhibits excellent soft magnetic properties combining high saturation magnetization with excellent permeability, and low coercivity values.[1,2] These excellent properties result from a random distribution of nanocrystals embedded within the amorphous matrix.[3,4] Previous investigations have reported that in case of FINEMET, Cu clusters act as heterogeneous nucleation sites for $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ nanocrystals and substantially reduce the crystallization temperature.[5–7] Using atom probe tomography (APT), Hono et al.[7,8] revealed that after short periods of annealing at 823 K (550 °C), Cu clusters form and act as heterogeneous nucleation sites for the $\alpha\text{-Fe}$ nanocrystals. Hono et al.[5] also proposed a model wherein the Cu clusters resided at the interface between the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ nanocrystal and the amorphous matrix. Independently, Ayers et al.[9,10] proposed that the similarity of the face-centered cubic (fcc) structure of the Cu clusters and the DO_3 structure of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ played an important role in the former acting as a nucleation site for the latter. However, in contrast to the model proposed by Hono et al.[5], Ayer et al.[9] proposed a model suggesting that the $\alpha\text{-Fe}$ nanocrystals form a shell, enveloping the heterogeneous nucleant Cu cluster at its core.

Nb is known to restrict the grain growth rate but different mechanisms have been proposed for how this is achieved. Yavari and Negri [11] suggested that a concentration gradient of Nb is developed at the crystal/amorphous interface, restricting the diffusion of Fe and Si. However, Mossbauer spectrometry studies have indicated that Nb diffuses out of the crystal and homogeneously diffuses into the amorphous matrix, which leads to the Nb concentration gradient.[12] Herman et al.[13] suggested that the combination of B and Nb act as diffusion barriers for nanocrystal growth.

While there have been extensive research efforts, including APT studies, focused on the FINEMET alloy composition containing both Cu and Nb,[5,9] there have been rather limited efforts on investigating FINEMET-like compositions that do not contain all of the alloying elements present in the commercial composition. A previous attempt was made to distinguish the roles of Cu and Nb in the FINEMET alloy, primarily based on transmission electron microscopy (TEM) studies.[14–17] For this purpose, four different alloy compositions were compared: $\text{Fe}_{77.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9$, $\text{Fe}_{76.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Cu}_1$, $\text{Fe}_{74.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Nb}_3$, and finally $\text{Fe}_{73.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Nb}_3\text{Cu}_1$, the commercial FINEMET composition. Combining DSC, XRD, TEM, and EELS techniques, they isolated the individual and combined contributions of the constituent elements on primary and secondary crystallization temperatures, activation energy, and microstructural evolution.[14–18]

This study will compare the detailed de-vitrification process in two rapidly solidified melt-spun alloy compositions: the FINEMET alloy with nominal composition listed previously and a model $\text{Fe}_{76.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Cu}_1$ alloy. As stated previously, Cu clustering at the early stages of de-vitrification is considered to be responsible for heterogeneous nucleation of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ nanocrystals.[5–10] Previous reports regarding the role of Nb are somewhat contradictory in terms of whether or not a Nb concentration gradient builds up at the nanocrystal/amorphous matrix interface and limits growth.[11–13] Furthermore, all the previous studies have addressed the roles of Cu and Nb on de-vitrification of the amorphous phase in an independent manner, since they have primarily focused on the FINEMET composition. However, the unique aspect of the present paper, which distinguishes it from previous studies, is that it focuses on rationalizing the coupled effects of Cu clustering and the role of Nb on the kinetics of growth of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ nanocrystals in the case of FINEMET compared to the non-Nb-containing $\text{Fe}_{73.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Nb}_3\text{Cu}_1$ alloy, using APT and TEM as the primary tools for investigation.

2. Experimental Section

Fe-based, melt-spun amorphous ribbons were used in these experiments. The ribbons were synthesized by rapidly quenching the molten alloy onto a spinning Cu wheel. The pre-alloyed powders are melted using an induction coil connected to 5 kW radio frequency generator. The processing chamber is made of stainless steel and contains a controlled high purity Argon gas environment. The chamber pressure is maintained at 0.4 to 0.5 atm. The Cu wheel was polished using a 1200 grit emery paper and cleaned with acetone prior to the experiment. The molten alloy was ejected through the bottom of the crucible with an orifice of $0.55 \text{ mm} \pm 0.05 \text{ mm}$ with an ejection pressure of $\sim 30 \text{ kPa}$. The ribbons had a composition of either $\text{Fe}_{76.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Cu}_1$ or $\text{Fe}_{73.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Nb}_3\text{Cu}_1$ and a thickness of $\sim 20 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. Heat treatments were conducted in a tube furnace at 823 K (550 °C) for 10, 15, and 60 minutes under an argon atmosphere. The needle-shaped tip samples for atom probe tomography (APT) were prepared using the focused ion beam milling technique (dual Beam FIB/FESEM Nova 200 system). A wedge-shaped lift-out sample was prepared and subsequently needle-like specimens were made by cutting sections from the wedge sample and attaching them to silicon posts on a micro-tip array. Subsequently, ion beam thinning/sharpening was carried out in multiple steps, starting with 30 kV ions followed by finishing with 5 kV ions to reduce the surface damage caused by the higher energy ions.[18] The final tip diameter of the atomprobe specimens was $\sim (50 \text{ to } 80) \text{ nm}$. Electron transparent transmission electron microscopy (TEM) samples were also prepared using the FIB technique. These samples were made by attaching a lift out prepared from the

sample onto a Cu grid using the micromanipulator. The thinning of the sample was carried out using a Ga ion beam at 30 kV. The final thinning of the sample for electron transparency was done at 5 kV with a Ga ion current of 0.12 nA to reduce the ion beam damage. TEM characterization was done on an FEI Tecnai F20TM TEM with a field emission source. APT was conducted on a Cameca LEAP 30009 HRTM through laser ionization with a pulse fraction of 0.2, pulse rate of 160 kHz, temperature of 30 K (-243 °C), and a pressure of 1×10^{10} Pa. The reconstructions were analyzed using Cameca's IVAS software.

3. Results

Detailed studies on phase evolution using XRD, and thermal analysis using DSC, of the two alloys investigated in the current study, for the relevant temperatures have been reported in a previous paper.[19] Atom probe tomography (APT) reconstructions from the melt-spun sample of the FINEMET (Fe_{73.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Nb₃Cu₁) alloy, exhibited a uniform distribution of Fe and other alloying elements (**Figures 1(a)** and **(b)**). While **Figure 1(a)** shows all the alloying elements (Fe in light blue, Si in red, B in dark blue, Nb in black, and Cu in orange), **Figure 1(b)** shows only Cu atoms in the atom probe reconstruction of melt-spun sample. On annealing at 673 K (400 °C) for 60 minutes, Cu-rich clusters form within the amorphous matrix (**Figures 1(c)** and **(d)**) due to the immiscibility of Cu in the Fe-base matrix. **Figure 1(c)** shows all Cu ions in the annealed FINEMET sample, while **Figure 1(d)** shows only Cu present in the Cu-enriched clusters within the APT reconstruction. This is in good agreement with previous reports of similar Cu clustering within the amorphous Fe-base matrix.[7] The no. density of Cu-rich clusters calculated from the APT reconstruction (**Figure 1(d)**) is $9.7 \times 10^{23} \text{ m}^{-3}$. Such Cu-rich cluster results were also seen in a Fe-Si-B-Cu system after similar annealing [683 K (410 °C) for 60 minutes] and APT.[20] In addition, these Cu clusters have been reported to act as potential heterogeneous nucleation sites for nucleation of α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals within the amorphous matrix.[9] Thus, the kinetics of Cu clustering contributes to the volume fraction and growth of Fe₃Si crystals.

Fig. 1 APT reconstructions from the FINEMET alloy as melt-spun (a, b) and after isothermal annealing at 673 K (400 °C) for 60 min (c, d). (a) Shows Si ions (red), B ions (blue), Nb ions (black), and Cu ions (red). (b) Shows only the Cu ions (red) in the as melt-spun sample. (c) Shows only Cu ions (red) after isothermal annealing at 673 K (400 °C) for 60 min. (d) Shows the Cu-rich clusters within the same reconstruction determined via cluster analysis algorithms.

The second set of annealing studies was carried out for both alloy compositions at 823 K (550 °C) for 10 minutes: the TEM results corresponding to this annealed condition are presented in **Figure 2**. **Figures 2(a)** to **(d)** show low magnification bright-field, low magnification dark-field, high magnification brightfield, and, high magnification dark-field images, respectively, from the 823 K (550 °C)/10 min Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ sample. In addition, a selected area electron diffraction pattern from this microstructure is shown as an inset in **Figure 2(a)**. The primary rings in this diffraction pattern can be consistently indexed based on the α -Fe₃Si phase. Based on this diffraction evidence it can be concluded that the nanocrystalline grains visible in **Figures 2(a)** to **(d)** belong to the α -Fe₃Si phase and their size range is from 50 to 100 nm.

Fig. 2 (a) A bright-field TEM image showing the α -Fe₃Si crystals within the retained amorphous matrix of the Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ alloy after isothermal annealing at 823 K (550 °C) for 10 min. Selected area electron diffraction pattern is shown as an inset. (b) Dark-field image corresponding to the bright-field image shown in (a). (c) Bright field and (d) Corresponding dark-field TEM images recorded at higher magnification of the α -Fe₃Si crystals within the same sample. (e) A bright-field TEM image showing the α -Fe₃Si crystals within the retained amorphous matrix of the FINEMET alloy after isothermal annealing at 823 K (550 °C) for 10 min. Selected area electron diffraction pattern is shown as an inset. (f) Dark-field image corresponding to the bright-field image shown in (e).

Figures 2(e) and **(f)** show bright-field and dark-field images, respectively, from the 823 K (550 °C)/10 min annealed Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ (FINEMET) sample. An electron diffraction pattern from the same sample, which can be consistently indexed based on the α -Fe₃Si phase, is shown as an inset in **Figure 2(e)**. Comparing, **Figures 2(c), (d), (e),** and **(f)**, which are at the same magnification, it is obvious that after 823 K (550 °C)/10 min annealing, the size of α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals is substantially smaller in the case of the FINEMET alloy compared with the Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ alloy. The size of α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals formed in the case of the FINEMET alloy is in the range of 5-10 nm, an order of magnitude smaller than those formed in the Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ alloy after an identical annealing treatment.

APT studies of the 823 K (550 °C)/10 min (short duration annealing) annealed condition for both alloys were carried out with the objective of determining the partitioning of the solute elements across the interface between the nanocrystals and the amorphous matrix as well as to get further insight into the size and enrichment within the Cu-rich clusters. Cu-rich clusters containing greater than 5 at. pct Cu have been delineated via isoconcentration surfaces (or isosurfaces in short), colored in green (**Figures 3(a)** and **(c)**), corresponding to the Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ and FINEMET alloys, respectively. These results clearly indicate that a substantially large no. of Cu clusters of 5 at. pct or more have developed in both alloys after 823 K (550 °C)/10 min annealing. The cluster no. density of 5 at. pct Cu clusters has been calculated to be $2.3 \times 10^{23} \text{ m}^{-3}$ in case of both Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ and FINEMET alloys.

Fig. 3 (a) APT reconstruction from the $\text{Fe}_{76.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Cu}_1$ alloy after isothermal annealing at 823 K (550 °C) for 10 min showing Si-rich regions as isoconcentration surfaces (red) and Cu-rich regions (>5 at. pct Cu) in green. (b) APT reconstruction from the $\text{Fe}_{76.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Cu}_1$ alloy after isothermal annealing at 823 K (550 °C) for 10 min showing Si-rich regions as isoconcentration surfaces (red) and Cu-rich regions (>20 at. pct Cu) in green. (c) APT reconstruction from the FINEMET alloy after isothermal annealing at 823 K (550 °C) for 10 min showing Si-rich regions as isoconcentration surfaces (red) and Cu-rich regions (>5 at. pct Cu) in green. (d) APT reconstruction from the FINEMET alloy after isothermal annealing at 823 K (550 °C) for 10 min showing Si-rich regions as isoconcentration surfaces (red) and Cu-rich regions (>20 at. pct Cu) in green.

In addition, the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ nanocrystals have been delineated via $B = 5$ at. pct isosurfaces, corresponding to B-depleted regions, plotted in red in **Figures 3(a)** and **(c)**. The reason for choosing the B isosurface to delineate the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ nanocrystals is because there is limited Si partitioning between the nanocrystal and the amorphous matrix during the early stages

of crystallization. Consequently, the Si isosurface appears very rough in these reconstructions. Also since Fe is the principal alloying addition, the variation of Fe across the α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals/amorphous matrix interface is not significant. Thus, concentration value of 5 at. pct for the B isosurface was chosen on the basis that the Si isosurface, delineating Si-rich regions, corresponded exactly to B-depleted regions. The no. density of α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals in case of Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ has been calculated to be approximately $2 \times 10^{22} \text{ m}^{-3}$, while in case of FINEMET it was calculated to be $6.8 \times 10^{22} \text{ m}^{-3}$ (varies by a factor of 3). While the α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals appear to be associated with Cu-rich clusters in both alloys, the substantial difference in no. densities of 5 at. pct Cu clusters vs that of the α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals indicates that all 5 at. pct Cu clusters are not acting as heterogeneous nucleation sites for nanocrystals. Therefore, for comparison, the most enriched Cu clusters, containing greater than 20 at. pct Cu, have been plotted as green isosurfaces in **Figures 3(b)** and **(d)**. The same figures also show the α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals via B = 5 at. pct isosurfaces, plotted in red. The no. densities of the 20 at. pct Cu clusters are $4.5 \times 10^{22} \text{ m}^{-3}$ in the case of Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ and $4.7 \times 10^{22} \text{ m}^{-3}$ in the case of the FINEMET alloy. Based on **Figures 3(b)** and **(d)**, it can be concluded that the most enriched Cu-rich clusters, containing at least 20 at. pct Cu, are associated with α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals. Furthermore, these APT results also reveal that α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals have grown substantially larger in the case of the Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ alloy compared with the FINEMET alloy for the same annealing treatment, corroborating the TEM results. These results clearly indicate the significant role played by Nb in constraining the growth of the α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals, since the only difference between the two alloy compositions is the absence of Nb in the Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ alloy.

Furthermore, it appears that the enrichment of Cu-rich clusters is also dependent on the presence of Nb in the alloy during short-term annealing [≤ 10 min/(823 K (550 °C))]. This is confirmed by the 1D composition profile corresponding to the Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ alloy, plotted by averaging across a 3-nm diameter cylinder, traversing across a α -Fe₃Si nanocrystal, the associated Cu-rich cluster, and the surrounding amorphous matrix (**Figure 4(a)**). Thus, in the case of the Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ alloy, the Cu-rich cluster exhibits a maximum core concentration of ~ 90 at. pct Cu (**Figure 4(a)**), while in the case of the FINEMET alloy, the Cu-rich clusters exhibit a much lower maximum core concentration of ~ 55 at. pct Cu (**Figure 4(b)**). Although **Figure 4** only illustrates one case, several such Cu-rich clusters present in the APT reconstruction were considered for each alloy and the results obtained were quite similar. Proximity histograms (or proxigrams) corresponding to Si, B, and Nb, have been plotted across the α -Fe₃Si nanocrystal/amorphous matrix interface, in the case of both the Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ alloy (**Figure 5(a)**) as well as FINEMET (**Figure 5(b)**) for short-term annealing (≤ 10 min/(823 K (550 °C))). These composition profiles clearly show that while Si partitioning is significant in the case of the

$\text{Fe}_{76.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Cu}_1$ alloy, locally changing from ~ 18 at. pct Si to ~ 10 at. pct Si across the nanocrystal/amorphous matrix interface, it is negligibly small in case of FINEMET (~ 14 at.pct Si constant across the interface). Similarly, B partitioning across the nanocrystal/amorphous interface is also substantially more, changing from ~ 2 at.pct B to ~ 15 at. pct B in case of the $\text{Fe}_{76.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Cu}_1$ alloy compared with FINEMET (~ 2 at. pct B to ~ 7.5 at. pct B). A distinct partitioning of Nb can also be observed in the case of the FINEMET alloy. The general partitioning trend appears to be an enrichment of B and Nb in the amorphous phase accompanied by partitioning of Si in the growing $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ phase. Annealing the FINEMET alloy at 823 K (550 °C) for 15 minutes resulted in substantial microstructural changes from the 10 minutes annealing case. Thus, TEM bright-field and dark-field micrographs indicate that after 15 minutes annealing (**Figures 6(a) and (b)**), $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ nanocrystals are from 10 to 15 nm in size and the no. density of crystals has greatly increased compared to the 10 minutes heat treatment (**Figures 2(e) and (f)**). This is also evident from the SAD pattern in the inset of **Figure 6(a)**. After an even longer term of annealing at 823 K (550 °C) for 60 minutes, the size range of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ nanocrystals and their no. density does not change significantly (**Figures 6(c) and (d)**).

Fig. 4 (a) 1D concentration profiles of Si, B, and Cu across the interface between the Cu-rich cluster and the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ crystal in case of the $\text{Fe}_{76.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Cu}_1$ alloy after isothermal annealing at 823 K (550 °C) for 10 min. (b) 1D concentration profiles of Si, B, Nb, and Cu across the interface between the Cu-rich cluster and the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ crystal in case of the FINEMET alloy after isothermal annealing at 823 K (550 °C) for 10 min.

Fig. 5 (a) Composition profiles of Si and B, plotted as proxigrams, across the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ crystal/amorphous matrix interface in case of the $\text{Fe}_{76.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Cu}_1$ alloy after isothermal annealing at 823 K (550 °C) for 10 min. (b) Composition profiles of Si, B, and Nb, plotted as proxigrams, across the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ crystal/amorphous matrix interface in case of the FINEMET alloy after isothermal annealing at 823 K (550 °C) for 10 min.

Fig. 6 (a) Bright-field and (b) corresponding dark-field TEM images $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ crystals in case of the FINEMET alloy after isothermal annealing at 823 K (550 °C) for 15 min. (c) Bright-field and (d) corresponding dark-field TEM images $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ crystals in case of the FINEMET alloy after isothermal annealing at 823 K (550 °C) for 60 min.

The APT analysis of the 823 K (550 °C)/15 min annealed FINEMET alloy (**Figure 7**) confirms a significant change in the volume fraction of α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals between 10 and 15 minutes of annealing (comparing with **Figures 3(c)** and **(d)**). **Figure 7(a)** shows the Cu ions (green), Si ions (red), B ions (blue), and Nb ions (black) within the 3D volume of an atom probe reconstruction for this heat treatment. **Figure 7(b)**, an APT reconstruction showing regions of more than 5 at. pct Cu (Cu-rich clusters in green) and less than 5 at. pct B (α -Fe₃Si regions in red) isosurfaces, clearly reveal that there is a larger volume fraction of α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals after 823 K(550 °C)/15 min annealing compared with 10 minutes annealing at the same temperature (compare with **Figures 3(c)** and **(d)**). It should be noted that the larger volume fraction of the crystalline phase led to overlaps of the 5 at. pct B isosurfaces, giving the impression of an interconnected network of the crystalline α -Fe₃Si phase. However, in reality, coupling the APT results with the previously discussed TEM results from the same sample (**Figures 6(a)** and **(b)**) clearly indicates that the α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals have increased in size and no. density.

Fig. 7 (a) APT reconstruction of the FINEMET alloy after isothermal annealing at 823 K (550 °C) for 15 min showing ions of Si (red), B (blue), Nb (black), and Cu (green). (b) APT reconstruction of the same sample showing isosurfaces of Si-rich regions (red) corresponding to the α -Fe₃Si crystals and Cu-rich regions (green). (c) Sections of the APT reconstruction capturing regions of the α -Fe₃Si crystals (red) joined to the adjacent Cu-rich cluster (green). (d) Composition profiles of Si, B, and Nb plotted as proximity histograms, across the α -Fe₃Si crystal/amorphous matrix interface in case of the FINEMET alloy after isothermal annealing at 823 K (550 °C) for 10 min. Note the Nb pile-up across this interface.

Figure 7(c) shows two higher magnification views of two distinct α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals in direct contact with Cu-rich (~20 at. pct Cu) clusters. This is direct evidence of the role of Cu clusters acting as heterogeneous nucleation sites for the α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals. Furthermore, it should be noted that the Cu clusters are attached to the side of the α -Fe₃Si nanocrystal in agreement with the previously proposed model.[5] In final, compositional profiles across the α -Fe₃Si/amorphous matrix interface for Si, B, and Nb, have been plotted as proximity histograms (**Figure 7(d)**). There are two noteworthy points regarding these composition profiles. First, Si partitioning across the nanocrystal/amorphous matrix interface locally changed from ~17 at. pct Si to ~11 at. pct Si, while B changed from ~1 at. pct B to ~10 at. pct B. Thus, it is clear that both Si and B have partitioned more than what was observed after 10 minutes, preferably due to the increased volume fraction of α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals. Second, the Nb profile clearly shows a distinct pile-up at this interface, which can act as a diffusion barrier to the growth of the α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals.

The results of longer term annealing of the Fe-Si-BCu and FINEMET alloys at 823 K (550 °C) for 60 minutes have been summarized in **Figures 8** and **9**, respectively. Interestingly, comparing the bright-field TEM images from the Fe-Si-B-Cu alloy for 823 K (550 °C)/60 min (**Figure 8(a)**), annealing reveals that the nanocrystals embedded in the amorphous matrix were about twice the size as compared with those imaged after 823 K (550 °C)/10 min (**Figure 2(a)**). Also, the atom probe composition profiles for these phases exhibit significant differences. A 3D map of Fe (light blue), Si (red), B (blue), and Cu (orange) ions within the reconstruction is shown in **Figure 8(b)**. The Cu cluster responsible for the nucleation of the adjoining α -Fe₃Si crystal is clearly visible in this reconstruction. In addition, the interface between the α -Fe₃Si crystal and B-rich amorphous matrix is also visible. The composition profiles for Si and B across the crystal/amorphous interface, shown in **Figure 8(c)**, clearly reveal that the α -Fe₃Si crystal contains ~19 at. pct Si after 823 K (550°C)/60 min annealing, while the B-enriched amorphous phase contains ~25 at. pct B. Furthermore, the Si content within the amorphous matrix and B content within the α -Fe₃Si crystal, both are nearly zero after the 773 K (500 °C)/60 min anneal. Thus, the partitioning of Si across the α -Fe₃Si crystal/amorphous interface, as well as the B partitioning across the same interface is substantially greater than that observed after 823 K (550 °C)/10 min annealing (~18 at. pct Si to ~10 at. pct Si and ~2 at. pct B to ~15 at. pct B across the nanocrystal/amorphous matrix interface). Another point to note is that unlike the local equilibrium established near the crystal/amorphous matrix interface in case of 823 K (550 °C)/10 min annealing (refer to **Figure 5(a)**), after the longer term isothermal anneal for 60 minutes, there is long-range equilibrium within both the crystalline and amorphous phases (**Figure 8(c)**). The composition profiles across the Cu cluster/ α -Fe₃Si crystal interface have also been plotted in **Figure 8(d)**. Two things are evident from these profiles; the Cu cluster is nearly elemental (~100 at. pct) Cu after the longer term anneal, as well as long-range equilibrium has been established in terms of compositional partitioning across this interface.

Fig. 8 (a) Bright-field TEM micrograph showing α -Fe₃Si crystals within the retained amorphous matrix of the Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ alloy after isothermal annealing at 823 K (550 °C) for 60 min. (b) APT reconstruction showing Si ions (red), B ions (blue), and Cu ions (green), in the same sample. (c) Composition profiles of B, Si, and Cu across the α -Fe₃Si crystal/amorphous matrix interface. (d) Composition profiles of B, Si, and Cu across the α -Fe₃Si crystal/Cu cluster interface.

Figure 9 summarizes the APT results from the 823 K (550 °C)/60 min annealed FINEMET alloy sample. The Si (red), B (blue), Nb (black), and Cu (orange) ions within the 3D volume of this reconstruction are shown in **Figure 9(b)**. One of the Cu clusters is visible in the top left corner of this reconstruction. The Si-rich nanocrystals, presumably corresponding to the α -Fe₃Si phase are highly refined in size and separated from each other by an amorphous wetting layer in between. In addition, a large B-rich region is visible on the right hand side of this reconstruction. The solute partitioning across the interface separating this large B-rich region and the adjoining α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals are shown using composition profiles for B, Si, Nb, and Cu (**Figure 9(a)**). Based on these profiles, it is clear that the large B-rich region contains ~ 26 at. pct B with no other solute atoms in any appreciable amount, indicating that this is possibly a grain of the Fe₃B phase, reported to form in FINEMET on long-term annealing.[17] The composition profiles shown in **Figure 9(c)** correspond to the interface between the α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals and the thin wetting amorphous layer separating them. Based on these profiles, it can be concluded that the α -Fe₃Si phase contains ~15 at. pct Si and also contains ~2 at. pct of both B and Nb. This is consistent with the composition profiles observed in case of the interface between the α -Fe₃Si phase and the Fe₃B crystal (shown in **Figure 9(a)**). The amorphous wetting layer separating these α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals has a composition of ~15 at. pct B, ~12 at. pct Nb, and ~10 at. pct Si. Therefore, it should be noted that while the amorphous phase separating the α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals contain a substantial amount

of Si and Nb, the grains of the Fe_3B phase, which form on long-term annealing, does not contain any Si or Nb.

Fig. 9 (a) Composition profiles of B, Si, and Cu across the Fe_3B /amorphous matrix interface of the FINEMET alloy after isothermal annealing at 823 K (550 °C) for 60 min. (b) APT reconstruction showing Si ions (red), B ions (blue), Nb ions (black), and Cu ions (green), in the same sample. (c) Composition profiles of B, Si, and Cu across the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ crystal/amorphous matrix interface.

4. Discussion

The nucleation and growth of the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ nanocrystals depend on the diffusion of different atomic species involved, in both crystalline as well as amorphous phases. Diffusion in amorphous materials is dependent on the fraction of excess free volume in these materials, the equivalent of lattice vacancies in crystalline materials.[22–24] In the present case, the ribbons were synthesized by a non-equilibrium melt-spinning process. Due to the nature of this process, all the as melt-spun samples are expected to contain substantial amounts of excess free volume. During the process of annealing, in the early stages, diffusion of atoms is rapid due to this excess free volume and a coupled process of atomic diffusion as well as the annihilation of free volume occurs simultaneously.[22] At later stages of annealing, all the excess free volume get either annihilated or

homogeneously re-distributed and the amorphous phase is structurally relaxed. Therefore, diffusion becomes very sluggish after structural relaxation of amorphous phase at longer annealing time periods.[22] This phenomena has been previously reported by measuring the diffusivity of Fe in the as-quenched $\text{Fe}_{40}\text{Ni}_{40}\text{B}_2$ amorphous alloys, and the observations indicated a reduction in diffusivity of Fe as a function of annealing temperature.[25] The relaxation effects in the present alloy systems are further discussed below. In the initial stages of annealing [673 K (400 °C)/10 min] (**Figure 1**), Cu clustering is observed in both $\text{Fe}_{76.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Cu}_1$ and $\text{Fe}_{76.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Cu}_1\text{Nb}_3$ (FINEMET) alloys and can be attributed to the positive enthalpy of mixing for Cu–Fe which is essentially an immiscible system. Thus, the negligible solubility of Cu in the parent Fe-base amorphous matrix becomes a strong driving force for cluster formation. The clusters formed at a low temperature [673 K (400 °C)], substantially below the crystallization temperature of the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ phase. Thus, the results are in good agreement with previous reports that Cu clustering occurs prior to crystallization.[9] It has also been reported by several authors that Cu clusters act as heterogeneous nucleation sites for the precipitation of the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ phase. The results presented in this paper (**Figures 3 and 7**), demonstrate a clear association between Cu-rich clusters and $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ nanocrystals, confirming the role of the former as heterogeneous nucleation sites for nanocrystals. Furthermore, the relatively larger volumes of the APT reconstructions presented in this paper, as compared to previous reports, clearly show that the Cu-rich clusters are joined to the surface of the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ nanocrystals, in agreement with the model proposed by Hono et al.[5] and not with the model proposed by Ayers et al.[9] One report also indicates a possible crystallographic orientation relationship between Cu-rich clusters and $\alpha\text{-Fe}$ nanocrystals in a soft magnetic Fe-Zr-B-Cu alloy,[21] presumably dictated by the low interfacial energy of certain well-matched planes between the two phases. The results presented in this paper allow a direct comparison of Cu-clustering process in FINEMET alloy vs the model $\text{Fe}_{76.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Cu}_1$ alloy, a similar alloy but not containing Nb. The APT results for short-term annealing duration (≤ 10 minutes) clearly indicate that for identical annealing conditions, both the size of Cu-rich clusters are smaller as well as their compositions are less enriched in the case of Nb-containing FINEMET compared to the $\text{Fe}_{76.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Cu}_1$ alloy (**Figures 3 and 4**). This indicates that the diffusion of Cu is restricted by the presence of Nb. Therefore, in case of the $\text{Fe}_{76.5}\text{Si}_{13.5}\text{B}_9\text{Cu}_1$ alloy, Cu can diffuse rather rapidly and form highly enriched Cu clusters in the initial stages of annealing before annihilation of free volume takes place, restricting overall diffusion kinetics. On the other hand, Cu diffusion is restricted in the presence of Nb for the case of the FINEMET alloy, and thus the amorphous phase is structurally relaxed before a sufficient no. of relatively larger size Cu-rich clusters can form. As noted earlier, these Cu-rich clusters can act as heterogeneous nucleation sites for $\alpha\text{-Fe}_3\text{Si}$ nanocrystals. However, the efficacy of Cu clusters as heterogeneous

nucleation sites appears to be directly dependent on the level of Cu enrichment. Thus, the results presented in this study clearly indicate that only the relatively higher Cu-containing clusters (with at least 20 at. pct Cu) act as potent α -Fe₃Si nucleation sites (shown in the APT results in **Figure 3**). This is further confirmed by the composition profiles across the α -Fe₃Si nanocrystal/Cu cluster/amorphous matrix (**Figures 4(a)** and **(b)**), wherein the Cu-rich cluster in the case of the Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ alloy reaches a peak composition \sim 90 at. pct Cu at its core, while in the case of FINEMET, the peak composition achieved at the core of the Cu-rich cluster is only \sim 55 at. pct Cu. In addition, it is also interesting to note that Nb not only restricts the diffusivity of Cu, but also the other elements, such as Fe and Si. Therefore, in the case of the Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ alloy, the absence of Nb results in much more rapid growth of the α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals compared to FINEMET. Crystallization in the case of the Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ alloy is growth dominated with relatively fewer α -Fe₃Si nuclei growing rather rapidly, the growth being dominated by diffusion of Si into the nanocrystals coupled with the diffusion of B out of the nanocrystals. In contrast, crystallization behavior of the Nb-containing FINEMET is rather different. Cu-rich clusters form in this alloy, but the slower diffusion of Cu results in smaller cluster sizes as well as less enrichment in these clusters. Due to the less pronounced enrichment of Cu in these clusters as well as their smaller sizes, many of these clusters may not act as potential α -Fe₃Si nucleation sites at the early stages of annealing (e.g., 823 K (550 °C)/10 min) (**Figures 2(e)** and **(f)**). Furthermore, in cases where one of these Cu-rich clusters nucleates a α -Fe₃Si nanocrystal, Nb is rejected by the growing nanocrystal and piles up at the amorphous/crystalline interface, acting as a diffusion barrier and substantially reducing the growth rate. These results clearly reveal the Nb pileup in substantially larger scale APT reconstructions (proxigrams in **Figures 5(b)** and **7(d)**), compared to those shown previously in one-dimensional atom probe studies on partially de-vitrified FINEMET alloys.[5] After annealing the FINEMET alloy for 15 minutes at 823 K (550 °C), there are many clusters that are both substantially enriched in Cu (greater than at least 20 at. pct) and of reasonable size (>3nm), potent nucleation sites for α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals. Therefore, a large no. of nucleation sites are activated, while the growth of the α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals is still limited due to Nb pile-up at the nanocrystal/amorphous matrix interface. Furthermore, Nb also slows down diffusion of Si as well as B. The overall result is that a much more refined microstructure (compared to the Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ alloy) is obtained with an average α -Fe₃Si nanocrystal size \sim 15 nm, as shown in the bright- and darkfield TEM images (**Figures 6(a)** and **(b)**).

Furthermore, it is interesting to note that the average size of nanocrystals remains nearly the same, even after prolonged annealing at the same temperature for 60 minutes (**Figures 6(c)** and **(d)**). As mentioned earlier, the presence of excess free volume in the amorphous matrix promotes diffusion during the early stages of annealing, resulting in

growth of the α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals. However, by the time these nanocrystals have grown to a certain size, the excess free volume of the amorphous matrix is largely annihilated or re-distributed and consequently restricts further diffusion of Fe, Si, and Cu. This effect coupled with the reduced diffusivity of these elements in the presence of Nb leads to rather limited diffusion in the matrix during the later stages of annealing (>60 minutes). The microstructure reaches a steady state without exhibiting substantial change with increasing annealing time. Subsequently, annealing at 823 K (550 °C) for extended time periods (~1 hour) can result in formation of other compounds, such as Fe₃B, as reported previously.[17] In addition, it should be noted that partitioning of Si and B between α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals and the adjacent amorphous matrix progressively increases after isothermal annealing at 823 K (550 °C) (10 minutes (**Figure 5(b)**) to 15 minutes (**Figure 7(d)**) and finally to 60 minutes (**Figure 9(c)**). Similarly, the partitioning of Si and B across the α -Fe₃Si crystal/amorphous interface in case of the Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ alloy also progressively increases from 823 K (550 °C)/10 minutes annealing (~18 at. pct Si to ~10 at. pct Si and ~2 at. pct B to ~15 at. pct B across the interface shown in Figure 5(a)) to 823 K (550 °C)/60 min annealing (~19 at. pct Si to ~0 at. pct Si and ~0 at. pct B to ~25 at. pct B across the interface shown in **Figure 8(c)**). Comparing these results for the FINEMET alloy with the Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ alloy clearly demonstrates the strong influence of Nb in reducing the diffusivity of other solute elements (Si, B, and Cu) in the amorphous matrix.

5. Summary

This paper presents a detailed comparison of the de-vitrification (or crystallization) pathways for two soft magnetic alloys, the commercial FINEMET alloy and the Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ alloy, which is based on the FINEMET composition but does not contain any Nb. The process of Cu clustering and the subsequent role played by these clusters as heterogeneous nucleation sites for the α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals has been investigated in a systematic manner. The emphasis of this study was on investigating the coupled effects of Cu clustering and Nb pile-up at the crystal/amorphous interface on the growth kinetics α -Fe₃Si nanocrystals using atom probe tomography and transmission electron microscopy. The effects of Nb and structural relaxation on Cu diffusion and subsequently on nucleation rate are compared for both the alloys. Furthermore, growth restricted de-vitrification took place in Finemet alloy, whereas growth dominated de-vitrification was observed for Fe_{76.5}Si_{13.5}B₉Cu₁ alloy resulting in a substantially refined microstructure for Finemet. This restricted growth can be attributed to Nb pile-up at the amorphous/crystal interface.

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